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BEYOND THE "BLACK BOX": THE URGENT CASE FOR UNIVERSAL STANDARDS IN CYTOMETRY

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Conflict of interests: None

Funding: CERCA, La Caixa, AGAUR

Acknowledgements: We thank the CERCA Program/Generalitat de Catalunya and the Germans Trias i Pujol Research Foundation for institutional support and acknowledge the financial support from Obra Social la Caixa. This work was also supported by Consolidated Research Group 2021 SGR 00002, AGAUR, Generalitat de Catalunya.

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Preface

While the biomedical community has long grappled with reagent integrity, the reproducibility crisis in 2026 has a more complex, systemic origin. Beyond "experiment-ruining" antibodies, the field of flow cytometry is increasingly undermined by a lack of technical transparency and the "black box" nature of modern data processing.

Cytometrists often rely on sophisticated machine learning, including manifold learning techniques like UMAP and t-SNE, and undisclosed axis transformations—such as biexponential scaling—to generate clean visual narratives. However, the choices of methods and their parametrization are frequently subjective and poorly documented, leading to significant interpretational bias and inconsistent results across laboratories. As the field celebrates 60 years of progress, the gap between high-dimensional discovery and clinical reliability remains alarmingly wide due to a lack of universal standards.

This article argues that establishing universal standards for data scaling, instrument calibration, and quality metrics is essential to move beyond analytical artifacts and to ensure rigorous validation in single-cell research.

Article

The 2024 News Feature, “The antibodies don’t work. The race to rid labs of molecules that ruin experiments” (6 November 2024), identified a critical fracture in biomedical research¹. However, as we navigate the research landscape of 2026, it is increasingly clear that the “reproducibility crisis” cannot be solved by focusing solely on reagent integrity. While antibody cross-reactivity remains a primary concern, the instrumental framework through which these molecules are analyzed when used as markers – most notably flow cytometry – is equally complicit in generating inconsistent results.

Yes, flow cytometry is uniquely vulnerable to antibody-related reproducibility failures. Its dependence on fluorochrome-conjugated antibodies makes it exquisitely sensitive to factors such as lot-to-lot variability, off-target binding, and inconsistent labeling ratios. Recent evaluations (particularly in immunophenotyping studies) have shown that even sequence-defined antibodies can exhibit substantial variability when conjugated to different dyes or sourced from different vendors. These discrepancies often remain undetected due to poor documentation and the absence of standardized validation pipelines. In multi-site studies, this variability leads to striking inter-lab differences in marker expression patterns, even when standardized protocols are followed.

However, we cannot blame only the antibodies: the systemic lack of attention to standardization and instrument calibration, poorly executed spectral unmixing, poor data visualization choices, and the inherent subjectivity of manual gating continue to undermine the reliability of high-dimensional single-cell analysis data.

Decades ago, the paper “Interpreting flow cytometry data: a guide for the perplexed” warned that data visualization techniques induce systematic interpretational bias². Today, our concern is especially timely, as last year the field celebrated the 60th anniversary of Mack Fulwyler’s seminal *Science* paper, which propelled flow cytometry to prominence in immunology and many other biological fields³. Since then, the field has accomplished enormous feats, moving from essentially single-fluorescence measurements to achieving remarkable levels of multiplexing through spectral cytometry, a combination of fluorescence spectroscopy with flow cytometry fluidics⁴.

However, the field that is so reliant on marker technologies (antibodies, fluorescent labels) and data processing (signal unmixing, sophisticated data representation, classification by Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI)) has reached such a level of complexity that many practitioners treat the instrument as a black box whose controls produce unreadable raw data. Those data are then processed by another black box (sophisticated software and its algorithms) to produce visualizations that confirm preexisting expectations, a form of confirmation bias that publication incentives reinforce.

This has a dramatic effect, as flow cytometry has become a routine mainstay of cell analysis across many fields, from clinical research to environmental biology. We are writing this letter to alert researchers, editors, and reviewers to a looming crisis in the reporting of data in a fundamental field of single-cell analysis. Paradoxically, this is especially evident in so-called “top-tier” journals, where the focus on new discoveries and novel phenomena leads reviewers to dismiss concerns raised by technology experts, resulting in many manuscripts built on a house of cards. Since cytometry is ubiquitous, we fear the problem is much bigger than many life scientists expect.

Although our list of issues may sound like a list of pet peeves from narrowly focused technical aficionados, each of the problems mentioned translates downstream into a set of serious consequences for experimentation and interpretation. We are often told, when complaining about problems with the technology misuse, that in the grand scheme of things, cytometry in a given experiment is just one element among many, and that the issue is too technically narrow to warrant any commentary, reaction, or even self-reflection on the part of the editorial staff. But if this is the case, why were these data presented to begin with?

One cannot help but experience the Gell-Mann Amnesia effect when opening a leading scientific journal, amazed by the progress in science, and then finding out that in the areas we actually know something about, the story is demonstrably inaccurate. We are surely just one pixel in the picture of life-science technology, and these same comments likely arrive from microscopists, mass spectrometrists, and others.

So, let us go through our list of red flags very briefly, and hope that the editorial staff treats them as a handy checklist when accepting manuscripts for their illustrious journal.

Undocumented Transformations and Scaling

First, even if the cytometry data is not processed through a pipeline of highly sophisticated ML/AI methods and is simply plotted in two dimensions, we already run into the first problem. Because fluorescence measurements exhibit heteroscedasticity (variance that increases proportionally with signal intensity), axis transformations are required to stabilize variance and enable meaningful visual comparison across the dynamic range. Logarithmic, biexponential, and hyperbolic arcsine transformations each accomplish this in different ways, and the choice of transformation and its parameters directly affects the apparent geometry of populations and, consequently, gating decisions.

Even with a simple logarithm, we may encounter problems because instrument preprocessing can yield negative values. More worryingly, the use of biexponential and hyperbolic arcsine transformations is typically undocumented in the visualizations. These are not purely aesthetic choices, as cytometrists perform what is called “gating”, that is, making conscious, human-driven selection of cellular populations by drawing regions of interest around them to either describe the biological system on the basis of the resulting statistical summaries (such as population frequencies, median fluorescence intensities, or derived ratios) or actually drive the physical sorting of the cells for research or therapeutic purposes. If we cannot recreate the axes in the plot, nor the regions we placed there, and the boundaries that were defined, how can we even approach reproducibility?

Serious errors, from improper biexponential scaling to “creative” gating designed to isolate nonexistent populations, remain alarmingly common in *Nature*, *Cell*, and *Science*. Different parameterizations of biexponential or hyperbolic arcsine scaling can produce dramatically different visualizations of the same data. These transformations are often selected informally (that is, by manually adjusting sliders based on how the plot “looks”), and the exact settings are rarely reported. This makes it nearly impossible to reproduce visualizations or replicate gating strategies. Visual adjustments made during data exploration must become reproducible and transparent, an issue that should ultimately be addressed at the vendor level.

This is important because the elementary mathematical transformations can distort the data in cytometry context, especially when analyzing cell populations with very low signal levels. As Parks et al. showed

over twenty years ago, logarithmic scaling can be particularly misleading because it creates a visual pile-up of low-signal events at the axis boundary and cannot display negative numbers, which often appear after compensation. They also demonstrated how this issue can be addressed using biexponential mapping⁵.

Figure 1 illustrates this principle using dot plots and contour plots of identical cytometry data displayed with logarithmic scaling (left panel) and biexponential transformation (right panel). The key point is that data transformation affects visualization, not the underlying data values; statistical calculations on raw data remain identical regardless of how the data are displayed (upper row, both panels). However, visualization profoundly influences gating decisions. Region A, drawn based on the left panel, appears to enclose a uniform population. Yet the biexponential transformation reveals that this same region captures only a subset of the true population, as low-fluorescence events are compressed and obscured in the logarithmic view (lower row, right panel). Clearly, biexponential scaling enables more accurate identification and selection of distinct populations that would otherwise be conflated or overlooked. Still, reproducing such plots requires access to the exact parameters of the biexponential transformation, which are often software-specific and not always transparently reported.

Figure 1. Logarithmic (left panel) and biexponential (right panel) displays of the same compensated flow cytometry data reveal dramatically different visualizations of cell populations. Both panels show pseudocolor and contour plots derived from a single sample. While data transformation does not alter statistical results (upper row), it significantly affects how populations appear. In the logarithmic display, 18% of events are compressed along the X-axis and are nearly invisible, especially in color plots. In contrast, the biexponential transformation redistributes these events, making them clearly visible and more accurately represented (right panel). Gate A illustrates this effect: although mean and median fluorescence intensities remain unchanged, the population captured within the gate differs substantially after transformation. This highlights how visual display can influence gating decisions despite identical underlying data. FlowJo software was used for all analyses.

Misapplication of Nonlinear Dimensionality Reduction

This lack of rigor extends to the misapplication of manifold learning techniques such as UMAP and t-SNE. The mathematical framework underlying UMAP rests on the assumption that the input data are

uniformly distributed on a locally connected Riemannian manifold⁶. Because real data rarely satisfy this assumption, the algorithm adaptively rescales the distance metric around each data point so that local neighborhoods appear uniformly dense. This rescaling step is sensitive to the fidelity of the input distances. When cytometry data exhibit heteroscedasticity, numerically equal differences no longer correspond to equivalent biological differences across the measurement range. The adaptive metric rescaling therefore operates on distances that are already inconsistent, compounding the distortion rather than correcting it. Without prior variance-stabilizing transformation, the resulting embeddings can misrepresent both the topology and the relative spacing of cell populations.

However, these techniques are often applied where their use is mathematically unjustified, leading to visualizations that are not only irreproducible but potentially misleading. So, the cytometry results are plagued by unexplained blob-like UMAP plots that are said to depict immune system changes and are supposed to provide us with deep insight into its function. The practitioners providing them often cannot explain the basis of the data representation or its sensitivity to parameter choices and small changes in the data. Other fields have come to recognize how dangerous a minefield this is, but cytometry has not⁷.

Opaque Fluorescence Panel Quality Metrics

Furthermore, there is a troubling lack of transparency regarding the quality metrics associated with fluorescence multiplexing in cytometry. A prominent example is the “Complexity Index.” Despite its name, this measure does not quantify “complexity” in any general sense; rather, it appears to be the square root of the condition number of the cosine similarity matrix derived from fluorochrome emission spectra. The condition number quantifies how sensitive spectral unmixing is to measurement noise, as higher values indicate spectra that are difficult to distinguish, leading to numerically unstable unmixing.

It is troubling, however, that this metric has not been documented in any peer-reviewed academic paper; it is simply a value reported by software used in commercial flow cytometry systems. Although mathematically trivial, the metric was introduced into the field of cytometry via a patent disclosure rather than rigorous academic analysis, yet many users rely on it without understanding its mathematical foundations or limitations.

A Path Toward Universal Standards

By 2026, it is evident that peer review still frequently prioritizes a “clean” visual narrative over the rigorous validation required to solve the reproducibility crisis. These publications frequently feature plots lacking essential technical transparency, such as proper representation of event density in dot plots (axes tick marks) or Fluorescence-Minus-One (FMO) controls.

Two recent publications in *Cytometry Part A* (2025) provide a path forward by demanding unified criteria. In “An Opportunity for ISAC and ICCS to Lead on Universal Cytometry Standards,” we argue that the gap between discovery and clinical practice can only be bridged through international leadership and standardized guidelines⁸. The danger of “experiment-ruining molecules” is most acute when measuring critical biomarkers, as exemplified in our review, “Transparency and reporting in PD-1 assessment by flow cytometry,” which reveals substantial technical inconsistencies in PD-1 measurement⁹.

In moving forward, the scientific community should reach a consensus that certain practices are no longer compatible with the requirements of contemporary peer-reviewed literature. It is essential that authors provide a complete and transparent sequence of inclusion/exclusion decisions in their analysis, utilize clearly defined negative controls for key populations, and ensure that fluorescence data scaling and transformations employed to improve visualization are both appropriate and fully documented. Additionally, reproducibility would be greatly enhanced by including absolute event counts for rare populations and ensuring the availability of raw flow cytometry data in public repositories.

Rather than viewing these as aspirational goals, they should be considered fundamental standards that enable readers and reviewers to verify that reported findings rest on rigorous biological measurements and not analytical artifacts.

Ultimately, the reliability of flow cytometry hinges on a collective commitment to transparency. By establishing and adhering to universal criteria, the scientific community can bridge the gap between benchtop discovery and patient care. To achieve this goal, the International Society for Advancement of Cytometry (ISAC) and the International Clinical Cytometry Society (ICCS) extend a hand to the global community to turn these standards into practice.

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Acknowledgements

We thank the CERCA Programme/Generalitat de Catalunya and the Germans Trias i Pujol Research Foundation for institutional support and acknowledge financial support from the Obra Social la Caixa. This work was also supported by Consolidated Research Group 2021 SGR 00002, AGAUR, Generalitat de Catalunya.